

Electrochemical behaviour of 3-(4'-sulphonamoylazo)-7-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarins

Rajeev Jain*, Priyanka Gupta and Akhilesh Bhadauria

School of Studies in Chemistry, Jiwaji University, Gwalior-474 011, Madhya Pradesh, India

E-mail : gwlsosmica@sancharnet.in

Manuscript received 5 October 2005, revised 29 August 2005, accepted 21 November 2005

Abstract : Electrochemical behaviour of 3-(4'-sulphonamoylazo)-7-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarins was studied in Britton-Robinson buffers in the pH range 2.5 to 12.0 at glassy carbon (gc) electrode. Cyclic voltammograms exhibited two irreversible peaks in the cathodic scan and one anodic peak at the far off reverse scan which has been assigned to the oxidation of phenolic group. Products of cpe was characterised by elemental and spectral analysis.

Keywords : Electrochemical behaviour, coumarine.

The study of the mechanism of reduction of azo coumarins at electrodes often parallels the metabolism of these compounds. Electrochemical behaviour of 3-(4'-sulphonamoylazo)-7-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarins have not been comprehensively investigated so far and in the present communication, a comprehensive electrochemical study has been undertaken at different H⁺ ion concentrations at solid electrodes.

Experimental

3-(4'-Sulphonamoylazo)-7-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarins having different substituents were prepared by the method

developed in the laboratory¹.

Synthesis of 3-(4'-sulphonamoylazo)-7-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarins :

Resorcinol (1.10 g, 0.01 mol) and 1-ethyl-2-(4'-sulphonamoyl)hydrazono-3-oxobutanoate (2.142 g, 0.01 mol) were dissolved in 10 mL sulphuric acid and the temperature of the solution mixture was maintained at 10 °C for 18 h. To this, 50 g of crushed ice was added. The solid so obtained was washed with 5% NaOH solution and then with water and recrystallised from ethanol, m.p. 195 °C, yield 65%. Purity of the synthesized compounds

Table 1. Electrochemical characteristics of 3-(4'-sulphonamoylazo)-7-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarins at GC and Pt electrodes, pH 6.5

Sl. no.	Working electrode	Concn. × 10 ⁻³ (M)	v	-E _{p,c I} (V)	-i _{p,c I} (μA)	-E _{p,c II} (V)	-i _{p,c II} (μA)	-E _{p,a} (V)	-I _{p,a} (μA)
1.	GC	0.5	50	0.62	9.30	1.07	9.81	-	-
			100	0.63	10.00	1.12	12.70	-	-
	Pt	0.5	50	-	-	-	1.15	8.53	
			100	-	-	-	1.09	12.60	
2.	GC	1.0	50	0.62	10.10	1.07	10.35	-	-
			100	0.63	11.00	1.08	14.20	-	-
	Pt	1.0	50	-	-	-	1.10	10.20	
			100	-	-	-	1.11	14.45	
3.	GC	1.5	50	0.62	10.50	1.13	11.22	-	-
			100	0.64	12.05	1.15	16.37	-	-
	Pt	1.5	50	-	-	-	1.12	11.04	
			100	-	-	-	1.09	17.00	

was checked by TLC. Similarly other compounds were synthesized and characterized by elemental and spectral analyses¹.

Controlled potential electrolysis studies were carried out on a BAS CV-27 cyclic voltammograph. Voltammograms were recorded on EG & G potentiostat (VersaStat II), integrated with Applied Electrochemistry Software (EChem.) A three electrode cell was used for the experiment. The cell consists of a glass container with a cap having holes for introducing electrodes and nitrogen gas. The working electrode was a glassy carbon electrode (GCE); the reference electrode was saturated calomel electrode (SCE) and auxiliary electrode was a platinum wire, which was directly poured in the solution. The GCE was washed and activated by triangular voltage sweep from +1.2 to -1.2 V at the scan rate (v) of 10-200 mV/s for 15 min.

AnalaR grade methanol was used as a solvent for preparing stock solutions ($1.0 \times 10^{-2} M$) of 3-(4'-acetylsulphonamoylazo)-7-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin and 3-(4'-guanylsulphonamoylazo)-7-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin.

Britton-Robinson buffers in the pH range 2.5 to 12.0 were prepared in doubly distilled water by adding suitable amounts of 0.4 M NaOH solution to a stock solution composed of a mixture of phosphoric acid, boric acid and glacial acetic acid. Solution was stirred and left overnight to attain equilibrium. All the chemicals used were of AnalaR grade. Nitrogen gas was passed into the solution for about 15 min and thereafter a blanket of nitrogen gas was maintained throughout the experiment.

Procedure :

Solutions for cyclic voltammetric study were prepared by mixing 1.0 mL of KCl (1.0 M), 1 mL of the stock solution of $1.0 \times 10^{-2} M$ 2.0 mL of methanol (which was necessary to prevent precipitation) and 6.0 mL of appropriate B.R. buffer. After deaerating, solution was taken in an electrochemical cell, and cyclic voltammograms were recorded at different scan rates ranging from 10 to 200 mV/s.

Controlled potential electrolysis :

Controlled potential electrolysis at glassy carbon electrode was carried out in a microcell. For this purpose a solution composed of 1.0 mL of depolariser, 6.0 mL of B.R. buffer, 2.0 mL of methanol and 1.0 mL of KCl was electrolysed by the application of a slightly higher potential than the peak potential. From the decrease of current

with time during electrolysis, the number of electrons transferred was calculated. Progress of the electrolysis was monitored by recording voltammograms at different interval of time, until only background current was realised. Number of electrons involved in the electrode process were evaluated by the application of formula : $Q = nFN$.

Results and discussion

Cyclic voltammograms of 3-(4'-sulphonamoylazo)-7-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarins in B.R. buffers of pH 2.5 to 12.0 at different sweep rates (10-200 mV/s) were recorded using glassy carbon as working electrode.

Both the compounds exhibited two irreversible peaks in the cathodic scan and one anodic peak at the far off reverse scan. Peak at higher potential has been assigned to the cathodic reduction of carbonyl grouping. At far off

Scheme 1

positive potential a small anodic peak has been assigned to the oxidation of phenolic group. Peak at less negative potential has been assigned to the reduction of azo group. Potential for this peak shifted towards more negative value with increase in scan rate as expected for irreversible electrode process². A plot of peak current vs $v^{1/2}$ is a straight line passing through the origin indicating the diffusion controlled nature of the electrode process. Effect of change in concentration on the electrode process has also been studied. Peak current increased with the concentration of depolarizer and peak current vs concentration plot is a straight line.

The plot of peak potential vs pH is linear up to pH 7.7 and after that there is small change in peak potential. The irreversible nature of the electrode process for the reduction of azo group (in contrast to the behaviour of azobenzene) observed for these compounds may be due to the bulky coumarin substituent present at one of the nitrogen of the azo linkage. Studies were also carried out on platinum electrode at various scan rates and concentrations at pH 6.5 (Table 1).

Reduction mechanism :

The cyclic voltammograms of the completely reduced

solution (after CPE) did not show any reduction peak indicates absence of electroactive species in the solution. The possible reduction sites in these compounds are cyclic $>C=C<$, $>C=O$ and exocyclic $-N=N-$. Out of these, the latter site is more susceptible to reduction. Second cathodic peak has been assigned to the reduction of $>C=O$ group. On the basis of the results of cyclic voltammetry, coulometry and CPE, following mechanism for the reduction of azo group in 3-(4'-sulphonamoylazo)-7-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarins may be postulated (Scheme 1). After the CPE the catholyte was tested for the presence of aromatic amine present but it did not give dye test, thereby showing that $-N=N-$ group is reduced to $-NH-NH-$ and further reduction of $-NH-NH-$ grouping is not taking place. This mechanism is further supported by the work of others⁴.

References

1. Priyanka Gupta, "Redox Behaviour of Organic Compounds at Solid Electrodes", PhD thesis submitted to Jiwaji University, Gwalior, 2002.
2. P. J. Hilson and P. B. Birnboorn, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1952, **48**, 478.
3. J. L. Sadler and A. J. Bard, *J Am Chem. Soc.*, 1968, **90**, 8.
4. M. Okimoto and T. Chiba, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1990, **55**, 1070, R. Jain, D. D. Agarwal and R. K. Shrivastava, *J. Electroanal Chem.*, 1991, **305**, 335.